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THE CLOUD COMPUTING SCENARIO IN WORLD

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ABSTRACT:

In a world where technology advances at a breakneck pace, the cloud computing industry has made a significant contribution to customer loyalty in a real-time environment. Cloud computing has resulted in a significant decrease in storage costs as well as more effective data collection and retrieval. Consumers with cloud providers make requests for a variety of services depending on their ever-changing needs. Due to a scarcity of services, providing all of the requested resources is difficult. Cloud service providers must ensure that their offerings are delivered in such a way that they satisfy the demands of their customers while still making effective use of resources. As a result, resource distribution is extremely important. This paper primarily focuses on emerging resource distribution methods, as well as comparisons and summaries of those techniques.

Keywords: Cloud storage, resource allocation, Cloud Computing Scenario

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Cloud Computing

The cloud infrastructure model is based on the resource sharing theory, which is a basic and efficient concept. We essentially exchange information over the internet in cloud computing, which means we store data in the cloud and a community of companies accesses it over the internet. Cloud computing refers to a set of networks that are linked together in a network to create an interface that can be scaled up or down, allowing data and software systems to access it [2]. There are two types of cloud computing models. The first is the Deployment Model, and the second is the Service Model.

1.2. Model for Implementation

How to reach the cloud is defined by the implementation model. Clouds can be grouped into four categories:

- **Public Cloud [1]:** Allows people to quickly and efficiently access applications and systems. Businesses, scholars, and government organizations can all own, run, and maintain it, and they can all work together. Amazon, Google, and Microsoft are some of the most well-known companies in the world.
- **Private Cloud [1]:** Provides customers with access to the organization's own resources and infrastructure. It can be purchased, controlled, and handled by the company itself, or it can be outsourced to a third party. IBM, Sun, and Oracle are only a couple of the firms that come to mind as examples.
- **Community Cloud [1]:** It offers resources to a network of organisations, and may be purchased, maintained, and managed by the organisations themselves or by a third party. Microsoft Government Group Cloud is an example of this kind of cloud.
- **Hybrid Cloud [1]:** This is a hybrid cloud that combines private cloud and public cloud, with the private cloud handling the most important and taxing operations and the public cloud handling the less critical and challenging ones. Microsoft Azure and VMware vcloud are two examples of cloud computing platforms.

1.3. Cloud Computing Resource Allocation

Resource allocation in cloud computing refers to the mechanism by which various cloud systems request different services in order to complete their activities over the internet. In a real-time cloud world, these various resources are distributed to cloud applications in order to complete server activities. Every independent unit is subjected to resource allocation strategies, which help service providers to make the most of their resources [2].

Resource distribution approach [13] combines the cloud's operations for allocating and using finite resources, which are included in the cloud's reach. An atmosphere that is suitable for a cloud application the application should be given the form and sum of money it requires in order to finish the job entirely. The order and timing of the resources are also critical for optimum distribution. The following circumstances should be avoided [13]:

- A resource conflict occurs as two applications want to use the same resource at the same time.
- When the amount of resources is limited, a condition called "lack of resources" occurs.
- Resource mutilation is a condition in which applications are withheld funding despite the fact that services are available.
- An under-provisioning condition happens where a small number of resources are available to a submission.
- If the application is allocated more money than it needs, an over-provisioning scenario happens.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

An updated round-robin algorithm for resource distribution in a real-time cloud system has been proposed by Pandaba Pradhan, Prafullu Ku. Behera, and BNB Ray [11]. The following two registers were used in this algorithm:

A threshold-based resource distribution in a real-time cloud environment has been suggested by Weiwei Lin, James Z. Wang, Cheng Liang, and Deyu Qi [10]. The key task of this strategy is to keep track of and forecast the resources that will be required, and then to effectively allocate those resources depending on the application's requirements. Because of two critical procedures, this scheme works. The first is the Broker, which runs alongside the programme on the client's physical computer, and the second is the Datacentre, which handles physical resources such as CPU and RAM. The datacenter waits for the broker to deliver the client's requests, and if additional services are needed to complete the request, it provides those resources. If there are insufficient resources, the excessive virtual resources are revoked.

MQLB-RAM [6] was suggested by Lixia Liu, Hong Mei, and Bing Xie, and it is based on different resource allocation techniques. The workload allocation and resource computing in a real-time cloud system is accomplished in this paper by allocating available resources to various machines, networks, or servers. It creates multi-QOS indexes by combining the needs of clients and cloud service providers. The needs of the customers, such as low cost, high performance method, and strong stable network, are fulfilled by using the load-balancing methodology and a continuous review on the load-balancer. The algorithm also calculates the disparity between the weights of each index in the peer to achieve load balancing while using energy and money efficiently.

Priority-based hierarchical resource distribution in a real-time cloud environment was introduced by Chandrasekhar S. Pawar and Rajnikant B. Wagh [9]. There is a dynamic solution to the varying workload of dynamic resource allocation. Digital computers are developed and relocated, as well as new resources are delegated or reserved. That's based on how long it takes to make a product. To achieve Service level agreement, the proposed algorithm responds dynamically to changing workload by preempting the lower priority task that is already being performed with the high priority task that has been dynamically introduced. If the priority of the two colliding tasks is identical, virtual machines are built from available resources.

The key problem, according to Marwa Hashim eawna, Salma Hamdy Mohammed, and El-Sayed M. El-Horbaty [5], was resource provisioning. In order to meet customer satisfaction, resource efficiency must be increased, and time and productive costs must be reduced. Suraj Pandey et al. proposed a scheduling heuristic based on Particle Swarm Optimization. The average computing cost was determined by running each application task on a variety of resources and ordering them by cost.

This paper recommends using a Simulated Annealing-based algorithm for job scheduling in cloud infrastructure. This scheme makes use of the principle of cooling and then freezing metal into a crystalline form with the least amount of energy. It starts at the original temperature T , then calculates the current expense and assigns a new benefit vector (NG) to it. When the computed NG is less than or equal to the current gain, the solution is adopted.

The resources present in each platform are managed by the scheduler of the VM, according to Hwa Min Lee, Young-Sik Jeong, Haeng Jin Jan [7]. It employs the Round Robin algorithm as well as the First Fit Greedy algorithm. If a node is considered to be the first in the Greedy algorithm, the VM's operator is selected as the host. Open Nebula is another open source tool that offers cloud resources through a variety of hardware platforms. It may be public, private, or a combination of the two. The Virtual Machine Scheduler, also known as the Matchmaking Scheduler, is used by Open Nebula to generate a priority list of available resources. Requirements and a pre-determined rank are used to produce the resource number, and the virtual machine is retained as the output. When the scheduler gets a virtual machine order, it discards all requests that do not meet the specifications.

3. THE TECHNIQUE OF RESOURCE ALLOCATION

The Round Robin Algorithm (1.1) is a type of algorithm that is used to solve a problem.

Round robin algorithms are mostly used in time-sharing applications. This is one of the most well-known and commonly used algorithms. It is thought to be extremely beneficial. The round robin algorithm is made up of a circular queue known as a ready queue, which is made up of processes waiting in line to be executed, and a quantum, which is a unit of time specified [11]. New processes are added to the end of the queue when they are created.

The first process is assigned to the CPU for one quantum of time in the round robin algorithm, and then the CPU dispatches the process. If the process is not finished during the quantum, it is deleted from the queue and extended to the end; otherwise, it is simply removed from the queue when this process' execution has been completed. If a process's execution time is shorter than one quantum, the process exits the CPU as soon as the execution is finished. The Shortest Job First Algorithm (SJFA) is an algorithm that prioritises the shortest jobs first.

The shortest task first technique, as its name implies, prioritises the processes that take the least amount of time to execute. It operates exactly the same manner as the FCFS algorithm, except instead of selecting the first job in the queue, it selects the shortest process instead. All processes are held in the ready queue in increasing order of their execution time, starting with the shortest job first. Following their placement in the ready list, they are given CPU time one by one to complete their processes [11].

The method of increasing the efficiency of a cloud environment by properly spreading the workload among various processors is known as load balancing. It ensures that no computer is completely loaded, partly loaded, or idle, and that the load is spread equally. The number of cloud users is increased every day, and as a result, the demand on the machines is rising. If not addressed, this can result in low system efficiency, resource waste, and customer frustration [7].

To improve reliability, resilience, and efficiency, as well as optimise resource usage, a good load balancing system should be used.

3.1 Algorithm for allocating services based on goals

Priority-based scheduling is a system for scheduling processes according to their importance. Any process is given a priority, and the process with the highest priority is carried out first. Where two projects of the same priority, they are completed in a round robin or first-come-first-served manner. It can be one of two kinds [10]:

- Pre-emptive: the CPU is pre-empted if the newly arrived processes have a greater priority than the current ones.
- Non-preemptive: when a new process is begun, the CPU is not preempted; instead, it is pushed to the front of the ready line.

3.2 Algorithm for Allocating Hybrid Resources

This technique is known as Hybrid Algorithm, and it is used in resource provisioning. This is a metaheuristic methodology for allocating services in a multi-tiered application that is used in cloud computing. Simulated Annealing is used as a scanning technique for global searches and then elects the global best position known as GBest. Particle Swarm Optimization is used as a searching technique for local searches and then elects the best position locally that is known as LBest. Simulated Annealing uses the global quest strategy to find the right GBest and then scans through it to find the best one [5]. The following is the algorithm [5]:

- Step 1: Begin by generating initial velocity and initial population.
- Step 2- Compute the magnitude of the objective function using the following equations:
 - If you're looking for something different (Where ST defines to be First Time, ECT implies Expected Completion time, DU means the Duration Time, EET signifies Estimated Execution Time and Finish Time is FT)
- Step 3- Now, define the original population based on the objective function values.
- Step 4- Now choose the best local location, also known as LBest.
- Step5: Using LBest as a reference, pick the GBest.
- Step 6- Ask SA to search the GBest for you. If the alternative proves to be superior to the previous GBest, replace it with the current GBest.
- Step7- The algorithm terminates when the last iteration is $i = i + 1$; otherwise, return to step4.
- Step8- Determine whether or not the GBest has to be relocated in order to obtain the desired result.

3.3. Algorithm that is based on results

In the cloud world, a performance-based resource allocation approach is used to allocate VMs in a consistent and orderly manner. A VM Allocation Management Manager as well as a Node Performance Analyzer are included in the setup. In its data centre, every provider has programme that performs scheduling operations [8]. The schedulers are in contact with one another. Decisions should be made based on experience of the actual statuses of the virtual machines. The aim is to assess each node's measurement capability and make use of the results. Two criteria are used to determine the output of a node. The memory's stored output and the CPU's computation time are two examples of this. The inverse matrix can be obtained using the LU decomposition. The following are the equations: [8]

The CPU selects the best node by weighing storage, node performance, and memory requirements.

When a cloud is given a job, the scheduler breaks it down into various subtasks using the resource allocation algorithm. The scheduler now assigns each cloud a specific assignment based on the input it has received from the other schedulers. The cloud service provider receives this order via the internet. These queries are distributed to various virtual machines that are capable of performing the specified task. Today, specialised techniques are used to build the virtual machines. The virtual machine scheduler receives information about the machine.

This algorithm is a load-balancing algorithm [3] that distributes the load among the available resources based on job sizes. It is based on a list of tasks, with certain resources being needed for all of them. The algorithm prioritises choosing and allocating resources to the task that requires the least amount of time to complete. A job is deleted from the task list after it has been finished. This algorithm is replicated before all of the tasks on the list have been completed.

3.4 Technique for allocating capital dynamically

The workload on applications fluctuates over time and over the course of a person's existence. The application may have deteriorated due to a lack of resources, or each resource may be underutilised and thereby wasted in a static resource allocation scheme [4]. This is due to the fact that users tend to use dynamic allocation techniques to accurately assign resources to applications based on their wishes, thus assisting in proper resource utilisation.

4. CONCLUSION

Cloud computing has ushered in a new era of computing by enhancing accessibility, connectivity, and security while also lowering costs and technology requirements. Since the number of cloud users is and over time, as are their rapidly evolving demands, it's critical to make the most use of the scarce resources available. Proper resource utilisation methods, when used wisely, will result in excellent data management and processing, as well as the most efficient use of finite resources. Various current resource distribution methods, as well as comparisons and possible alternatives by various scholars, have been explored in this article.

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